

TEMPERATURE EFFECT ON THE STRESS CONCENTRATION IN
THE COMPOSITE MATERIAL USED BY THE X-29A FORWARD-SWEPT
WING AIRCRAFT

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ABSTRACT

The theory of anisotropic elasticity was used to evaluate the anisotropic stress concentration factors of a composite laminated plate containing a small circular hole. This advanced composite material was used to manufacture the X-29A forward-swept wing. The stress concentration factor of the usual isotropic materials is three. However, it was found that for composite materials, the anisotropic stress concentration factor is no longer a constant, and that the locations of maximum tangential stress points could shift by changing the fiber orientation with respect to the loading axis. The analysis showed that through the lamination process, the stress concentration factor could be reduced drastically, and therefore the structural performance could be improved. Both the mixture rule approach and the constant strain approach were used to calculate the stress concentration factor of room temperature. The results predicted by the mixture rule approach were about twenty percent deviate from the experimental data. However, the results predicted by the constant strain approach matched the testing data very well. This showed the importance of the inplane shear effect on the evaluation of stress concentration factor for the X-29A composite plate.

At low temperature (-60°F), the results predicted by the mixture rule approach provided good correlation with the experimental data. At elevated temperature (200°F), the results calculated from the constant strain approach were about ten percent conservative than the experimental data. These showed both the advantages and the limitations of different analytical models in predicting stress concentration factors at various temperature levels. Furthermore, the experimental data showed the stress concentration factors decreased as the temperature increased.

INTRODUCTION

The X-29A advanced technology demonstrator is sponsored by the Defense Advanced Research Projects Agency with support from NASA and the Air Force.

The X-29A features a unique forward-swept wing (Fig. 1), made of composite materials which offers weight reduction of as much as 20 percent in comparison with convention aft-swept wings.

A forward-swept wing is prone to structural divergence, because as dynamic pressure increases, forces tend to bend the leading edge up.

If a divergent speed were reached, a cycle of leading edge bending, increased local angle of attack and greater wing loading could grow to cause a structural failure. The wing's high rigidity prevents divergence from occurring within the X-29's flight envelope.

Because of their importance in aircraft design application, laminated, continuous-fiber reinforced-resin matrix composites containing through cutouts have been the subject of considerable study (ref. 1 to 6). In this paper, anisotropic plate theory was used to calculate the anisotropic stress concentration factors (SCF) for the X-29A composite plate containing a circular hole.

ANALYSIS

Let axes 1,2 be the principal coordinate axes of the laminated plate, and let axes L,T be the principal material axes of the single composite ply shown in figure 2.

For an anisotropic plate containing a circular hole subjected to remote uniaxial tensile stress σ_∞ , acting at an angle ϕ with respect to the principal elastic axis 1 of the plate (fig. 3), the tangential stress, σ_α and tangential stress concentration factor, $K \equiv \sigma_\alpha/\sigma_\phi$ along the circular hole boundary may be expressed as (ref.3)

$$K \equiv \frac{\sigma_\alpha}{\sigma_\infty} = \frac{E_\alpha}{E_1} \{ [-\cos^2 \phi + (k+n) \sin^2 \phi] k \cos^2 \alpha + [(1+n) \cos^2 \phi - k \sin^2 \phi] \sin^2 \alpha - n(1+k+n) \sin \phi \cos \phi \sin \alpha \cos \alpha \}$$

where E_α is the modulus of elasticity in the α direction (fig. 3)

To evaluate the modulus of elasticity of a laminated plate, both the mixture rule approach and the constant strain approach could be used. In the mixture rule approach, the transformed ply-elastic constants (\bar{E}_1, \bar{E}_2 , etc.) with respect to the {1, 2} system can be related to the material constants (E_L, E_T , etc.) with respect to the {L, T} system through the transformation equations (ref. 3).

If the composite plate is made of N number of single plies with different fiber orientations, then by using the mixture rule, the engineering elastic constants { $\bar{E}_1, \bar{E}_2, \bar{G}_{12}, \bar{\nu}_{12}, \bar{\nu}_{21}$ } for the composite plate can be written as (ref. 1)

$$\bar{E}_1 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N \bar{E}_1(\theta_j) \quad \bar{E}_2 = \frac{1}{N} \sum_{j=1}^N \bar{E}_2(\theta_j) \quad \text{etc.}$$

In the constant strain approach, it is assumed that the strain remains constant across the laminate thickness and the inplane stress-strain relation for a laminate is used and it is actually the stress resultant versus inplane strain relation. (ref. 5 and 6)

The calculation of the effective engineering elastic constants { $\bar{E}_1, \bar{E}_2, \bar{G}_{12}, \bar{\nu}_{12}$ } is performed by relating the compliance components to inplane engineering constants under uniaxial tension along the 1-axis (ref. 7).

RESULTS

The X-29A forward-swept wing composite plate is made up of 40-plyies with the total thickness of .56 cm (.22 in.). The stacking sequence and the ply-engineering elastic constants are given by

$$[\pm 45|0_4|\pm 45|90_2|\pm 45|0_4|\pm 45|0_2]_s$$

-60°F	70°F	200°F
$E_L = 19.23 \times 10^6 \text{psi}$	$E_L = 18.76 \times 10^6 \text{psi}$	$E_L = 18.29 \times 10^6 \text{psi}$
$E_T = 1.71 \times 10^6 \text{psi}$	$E_T = 1.57 \times 10^6 \text{psi}$	$E_T = 1.44 \times 10^6 \text{psi}$
$G_{LT} = 0.858 \times 10^6 \text{psi}$	$G_{LT} = 0.82 \times 10^6 \text{psi}$	$G_{LT} = 0.785 \times 10^6 \text{psi}$
$\nu_{LT} = 0.312$	$\nu_{LT} = 0.312$	$\nu_{LT} = 0.312$

The tangential stresses σ_α around a circular hole in a laminated X-29A composite plate were calculated for three loading cases: $\phi = 0$ (loading in axis-1 direction), $\phi = \frac{\pi}{4}$, and $\phi = \frac{\pi}{2}$ (loading in axis-2 direction). The results obtained from the constant strain approach and the mixture rule approach of three different temperature levels (-60°F, 70°F, and 200°F) are shown in Table I.

Figures 4 and 5 indicate that the locations of the maximum tangential stress points could shift by changing the fiber orientation with respect to the loading axis. In figure 6, it shows that at elevated temperature (200°F), the maximum stress concentration factor K reached the peak value of 3 at four locations ($\alpha = 120^\circ, 300^\circ$ by constant strain approach and $\alpha = 105^\circ$ and 285° by mixture rule approach).

CONCLUSION

The theory of anisotropic elasticity was used to evaluate the anisotropic stress concentration factors for laminated OBX-29A (forward-swept wing) research aircraft composite plates of three different temperature levels.

It is well known that the usual isotropic material stress concentration factor is three. However, the analysis showed that the anisotropic stress concentration factor could be greater or less than three for composite materials, and the locations of the maximum tangential stress points could shift by the change of fiber orientation with respect to the loading axis.

Both the mixture rule approach and the constant strain approach were used to calculate stress concentration factors of room temperature. The results obtained by the mixture rule approach were about twenty percent deviate from the experimental data. However, the results predicted by the constant strain approach matched the testing data very well. This showed the importance of the inplane shear effect on the evaluation of stress concentration factors for the laminated X-29A composite plate. A further investigation about the inplane shear effect will need a three dimensional model from anisotropic elasticity plus the interlaminar stress analysis.

At low temperature (-60°F), the results predicted by the mixture rule approach provided good correlation with the experimental data. At elevated temperature (200°F), the results calculated from the constant strain approach were about ten to fifteen percent more conservative than the experimental data. These showed both the advantages and the limitations of different analytical models in predicting stress concentration factors at various temperature levels. Furthermore, the experimental data showed the stress concentration factors decreased as the temperature increased.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

This work was supported by the NASA-ASEE Summer Faculty Fellowship in 1988. The author is greatly indebted to Donald C. Bacon, Jr., assistant chief of research engineering division, V. Michael DeAngelis, branch chief of aerostructures, Don Black, deputy branch chief of aerostructures, Lawrence F. Reardon, group leader of structural test operation and Dr. William L. Ko, aerospace engineer for invaluable advice, experimental data collection and helpful discussions.

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ECN 32396

Figure 1. X-29A airplane.

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Figure 2. Rotation from material axis L to laminated plate axis 1.

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Figure 3. Tension at an angle to a principal elastic axis 1 of an anisotropic plate with a circular hole.

STRESS CONCENTRATION FACTOR CORRELATION

DATA FOR PHI = 0° ALPHA = 90°									
LOAD (LBS)	-60°F			70°F			200°F		
	SCF EXPM T	SCF MIX RULE	SCF CNST STRAIN	SCF EXPM T	SCF MIX RULE	SCF CNST STRAIN	SCF EXPM T	SCF MIX RULE	SCF CNST STRAIN
600	4.09	4.53	3.71	3.53	4.58	3.71	3.00	4.64	3.72
1000	4.36	4.53	3.71	3.71	4.58	3.71	3.22	4.64	3.72
2000	4.36	4.53	3.71	3.98	4.58	3.71	3.29	4.64	3.72
3000	4.36	4.53	3.71	3.88	4.58	3.71	3.39	4.64	3.72
4000	4.36	4.53	3.71	3.84	4.58	3.71	3.38	4.64	3.72

Table I

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Figure 4. SCF of X-29 laminated plate (constant strain).

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Figure 5. SCF of X-29 laminated plate (constant strain).

SCF CORRELATION FOR $\phi = 45^\circ, 200^\circ \text{ F}$

Figure 6. ALPHA (DEG)